

BIR ARGUMENTNING FUNKSIYALARI QATNASHGAN BA’ZI TRIGONOMETRIK TENGLAMALARNING YECHIMLARI

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ayrim trigonometrik tenglamalarni universal almashtirish formulalari yordamida yechish keltirilgan.

Hamma trigonometrik funksiyalarni $\sin x$ va $\cos x$ lar orqali ifodalash mumkin bo‘lgani uchun, bir argumentning trigonometrik funksiyalariga nisbatan ratsional tenglamalarni

$$R(\sin x, \cos x) = 0$$

ko‘rinishida yozish mumkin (bunda R ifoda $\sin x$ va $\cos x$ ga nisbatan ratsional funksiya).

$R(\sin x, \cos x) = 0$ ko‘rinishdagi tenglamalarni $tg \frac{x}{2}$ ga nisbatan ratsional bo‘lgan tenglamalarga keltirib yechish mumkin.

1-misol. $3 \sin x + \sqrt{3} \cos x = 3$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. Tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi: $(-\infty, +\infty)$. $\sin x$ va $\cos x$ larni universal almashtirish formulalaridan foydalanib almashtirsak,

$$3 \cdot \frac{2tg \frac{x}{2}}{1-tg^2 \frac{x}{2}} + \sqrt{3} \cdot \frac{1-tg^2 \frac{x}{2}}{1+tg^2 \frac{x}{2}} = 3$$

tenglamadan

$$(\sqrt{3}+1)tg^2 \frac{x}{2} - 2\sqrt{3}tg \frac{x}{2} + (\sqrt{3}-1) = 0$$

Tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Buni yechsak,

$$tg \frac{x_1}{2} = 1 \text{ dan } \frac{x_1}{2} = \frac{\pi}{4} + k\pi \text{ yoki } x_1 = \frac{\pi}{2} + 2k\pi.$$

$$\operatorname{tg} \frac{x_2}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{3}-1}{\sqrt{3}+1} \text{ dan } \frac{x_2}{2} = \operatorname{arctg} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}-1}{\sqrt{3}+1} \right) + k\pi$$

yoki

$$x_2 = 2\operatorname{arctg} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}-1}{\sqrt{3}+1} \right) + 2k\pi.$$

Lekin almashtirish natijasida berilgan tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi $x=\pi(2k+1)$ ga kichraygan edi. $x=\pi(2k+1)$ qiymatlarning berilgan tenglamaning yechimlari bo‘lish-bo‘lmasligini tekshiramiz. Buning uchun $\sin x$ va $\cos x$ larning davri 2π bo‘lgani uchun $x=\pi$ ni tekshirsak kifoya, ya’ni

$$3 \sin \pi + \sqrt{3} \cos \pi = 3 \text{ yoki } -\sqrt{3} \neq 3.$$

Demak, $x=\pi(2k+1)$ tenglamaning yechimi bo‘la olmaydi.

$$\text{Javob: } x_1 = \frac{\pi}{2}(4k+1); \quad x_2 = 2\operatorname{arctg} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}-1}{\sqrt{3}+1} \right) + 2k\pi.$$

2-misol. $\sin^2 x + 0.5 \sin 2x + 2 \cos x = 2$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. Tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi: $(-\infty, +\infty)$. $\sin x$ va $\cos x$ larni $\operatorname{tg} \frac{x}{2}$

ga almashtirib,

$$\left(\frac{2\operatorname{tg} \frac{x}{2}}{1-\operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2}} \right)^2 + 0.5 \cdot 2 \frac{2\operatorname{tg} \frac{x}{2}}{1-\operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2}} \cdot \frac{1-\operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2}}{1+\operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2}} + 2 \frac{1-\operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2}}{1+\operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2}} = 2$$

tenglamadan

$\operatorname{tg}^3 \frac{x}{2} - \operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2} - \operatorname{tg} \frac{x}{2} = 0$ yoki $\operatorname{tg} \frac{x}{2} = 0$ va $\operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{x}{2} - \operatorname{tg} \frac{x}{2} - 1 = 0$ tenglamalarni hosil qilamiz.

Bu tenglamalarni yechib,

$$x_1 = 2\pi k \text{ va } x_{2,3} = 2\operatorname{arctg} \left(\frac{1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2} \right) + 2k\pi$$

larni topamiz. Lekin almashtirish natijasida berilgan tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi $x=\pi(2k+1)$ ga kichraygan edi. Tenglamani $x=\pi$ da tekshiramiz, ya’ni

$$\sin^2 \pi + 0.5 \sin 2\pi + 2 \cos \pi = 2 \text{ yoki } -2 \neq 2.$$

Demak, $x = \pi(2k+1)$ tenglamaning yechimlari emas.

$$\text{Javob: } x_1 = 2\pi k, \quad x_{2,3} = 2 \operatorname{arctg} \left(\frac{1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2} \right) + 2k\pi.$$

$\sin x$, $\cos x$ $\operatorname{tg} x$ va $\operatorname{ctg} x$ larni $\operatorname{tg} \frac{x}{2}$ ga almashtirish universal trigonometrik almashtirish deyiladi. Bu almashtirish faqat tenglamalarga boshqa almashtirishlarni ishlatish mumkin bo‘lmagan hollardagina ishlatiladi, chunki natijada yuqori darajali tenglamalar hosil bo‘lishi mumkin.

$a \sin x + b \cos x = c$ ko‘rinishidagi tenglamalarni yechish.

$a \sin x + b \cos x = c$ ko‘rinishidagi tenglama, (a , b , c lar o‘zgarmas sonlar) $R(\sin x, \cos x) = 0$ tenglamaning hususiy holi bo‘lib, uni universal almashtirish yordami bilan yechish mumkin. Bu tenglama quyidagicha ham yechiladi.

Tenglamani

$$\frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \sin x + \frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \cos x = \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}$$

ko‘rinishida yozib,

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}, \quad \sin \varphi = \frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}$$

deb olsak,

$$\cos \varphi \sin x + \sin \varphi \cos x = \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}$$

ni hosil qilamiz. Bundan

$$\sin(\varphi + x) = \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}.$$

U holda $\left| \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \right| \leq 1$ bo‘lsa, tenglamaning yechimlari

$$x + \varphi = (-1)^n \arcsin \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} + \pi k \text{ yoki}$$

$x = (-1)^n \arcsin \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} - \varphi + \pi k$ bo‘lib $\left| \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \right| > 1$ bo‘lsa, tenglama yechimga ega

emas.

3-misol. $\sin x + \sqrt{3} \cos x = \sqrt{2}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. tenglamaning ikkala tomonini $\sqrt{1^2 + \sqrt{3}^2} = 2$ ga bo‘lib,

$$\frac{1}{2} \sin x + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \cos x = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$$

ni hosil qilamiz.

$$\cos \frac{\pi}{3} = \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{va} \quad \sin \frac{\pi}{3} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

Bo‘lgani uchun, yuqoridagi tenglama

$$\cos \frac{\pi}{3} \sin x + \sin \frac{\pi}{3} \cos x = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$$

yoki

$$\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + x\right) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$$

ko‘rinishga keladi. Bu yerdan

$$x + \frac{\pi}{3} = (-1)^n \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi k$$

yoki

$$x = (-1)^n \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\pi}{3} + \pi k.$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

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